

Appendix D: Codes

The following tables give an overview and description of all codes used during the coding process. This encompasses high-, medium-, and low-level codes.

Table 1: Overview and description of the high-level codes used for the coding process.

High-level Codes	Description
demographics	demographic information on the background of the interviewees. Also for company/product background descriptions.
development practices	development practices currently in use for AI systems, e.g., CI/CD pipeline, data collection/ analysis, continuous training, evaluation, testing, and monitoring.
initial AIA thoughts	broad opening of the AIA part of the interview.
current AIA addressing	how interviewee's company currently addresses the AIA, e.g., involved departments and priorities.
high-risk AI scenario	relates to the whole high-risk scenario interview part. Used only if no "req [...]" code applies within the high-risk req part.
req risk & quality mgt	thematic section of related requirement.
req data governance	thematic section of related requirement.
req acc, robust, cyber-sec	thematic section of related requirement.
req transparency	thematic section of related requirement.
req human oversight	thematic section of related requirement.

req record-keeping	thematic section of related requirement.
req technical doc	thematic section of related requirement.
compliance challenge	how challenging the interviewee deems AIA compliance after exposure to high-risk requirements through the interview.
company/ industry impact	AIA's impact on interviewees company.
voluntary compliance	voluntary compliance to certain parts of the AIA, even when not developing high-risk AI systems.
interviewee initiative	when an interviewee has something to add during the interview that is not covered by our questions.

Table 2: Overview and description of the medium-level codes used for the coding process.

Medium-level Codes	Description
current role	current professional role at the company.
previous roles	previous professional roles, possibly also at other companies or self-employed.
AI/ML proficiency	interviewee's perceived competence on the topic of AI/ML.
regulatory req backgr	interviewee's perceived competence on regulatory requirements.
graduation year	interviewee's graduation year of highest completed education.
educational back-ground	interviewee's educational background, like the field of study.
start year at company	start year at the company where the interviewee is currently employed.
continuous eng practices	concerning continuous engineering practices, e.g., CI/CD pipelines, data collection/analysis, continuous training, evaluation, testing, and monitoring.

model update/release freq	up-	about the practice of how often ML models that are currently in use are updated or re-released.
involved departments	depart-	which departments are involved in the current addressing of the AIA within the organization.
current AIA priorities	priori-	for the current addressing and prioritization of the AIA within the organization.
current methods/techniques	meth-	about methods/approaches/techniques already in place at the interviewee's company that could be mapped to the act's high-risk requirements.
lacking solution		for AIA requirements or general challenges where currently no methods/approaches/techniques in terms of solutions are implemented at the interviewee's company.
req most challenging	challeng-	for high-risk requirement considered especially challenging by the interviewee. The code is only used for answers to the related interview sub-question at the end of the high-risk scenario part.
req easy to comply with	comply with	for high-risk requirements that are considered not challenging to implement/comply with.
external expertise	expertise	for whether external expertise might be needed for implementation of the high-risk requirements.
pos/opportunity	optimistic/	for a positive/optimistic interviewee sentiment that could be focused, e.g., on the opportunities of something.
neg/limitation	pessimistic/	for a negative/pessimistic interviewee sentiment that could be focused, e.g., on the limitations of something.
challenge		when something is identified as challenging by the interviewee.
uncertainty		when uncertainty is voiced, e.g., the scope of a regulation.

suggested solution	when some solution for a problem is described.
company/ product background	for when the interviewee describes what their product or service is about.

Table 3: Overview and description of the low-level codes used for the coding process.

Low-level Codes	Description
ML model	for aspects connected to the ML model.
CI/CD	CI/CD practices.
testing	everything testing related.
monitoring/ logging	all monitoring and logging activities, including record-keeping in general.
workload	extra work, e.g., for implementing the AIA.
product scope	what a product/service can do (features) and where it can be deployed (use cases).
planning security	concerning clear regulatory boundaries and consequently expectation clarity/management.
business opportunity	for a single actor or group of actors – when there is a new way of doing business emerging.
strategic decision	for strategic decisions of companies, e.g., not to include facial recognition in their products.
workplace culture	cultural aspects related to employee management, training initiatives, and company values.
competitiveness	when at least two types of actors are involved that compete in some way with each other, e.g., concerning location (Europe vs. the rest of the world), or company size.
bias	everything bias related.
accuracy	related to model prediction accuracy.
robustness	related to AI system robustness.
cybersecurity	everything security-related, e.g., types of attacks.

validation	regarding validating levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity (demanded in transparency requirement).
extra cost	for aspects considered to add extra monetary costs, e.g., regarding compliance with the act.
marketing	impacts on companies' marketing (positive or negative).
interpretability	related to the interpretability of AI systems.
state-of-the-art	when it is referred to the state-of-the-art.
environmental impact	mostly related to the requirement of record-keeping regarding energy/resource usage logging and documentation.
trustworthiness	everything trust-related, e.g., trust in the ML model and its predictions, or trust in a company as a whole.
explainability	e.g., related to the transparency requirement, or the right to explanation of individual decision-making.
data	for data-related aspects, e.g., data management, data quality, data governance.
legal	for general legal aspects, e.g., existing regulations that apply (regulatory environment).
GDPR	for references to or comparisons with GDPR.
transparency	for transparency-related aspects.
benchmarking	about internal and external benchmarking.
ethics	all ethical aspects.
general purpose AI	formerly called foundation models. Separate from high-risk requirements.
data recency	about how up-to-date the training, test, and validation datasets are.
customer power	for when something depends on the customer or when customers are in control over an asset, e.g., logging data.
recertification burden	when the obligation to re-certify one's system after bigger changes has a negative impact on update cycles.